

CLINICAL-INSTRUMENTAL AND NEUROLOGICAL COMPLICATIONS IN JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS IN CHILDREN

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The aim of the study. To study diagnostic criteria of neurological complications in patients with YRA.

Materials and methods of the study. We observed children in cardiolummatological department of TashPMI clinic. The study included 45 children aged 4 to 18 years with a clinical diagnosis of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (YRA). In the neurological status of children, 38 (84%) examined children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis: headache - 9 children (24%), paresthesia and numbness in distal limb - 7 (18%), cramps (hyperkinesis) - 4 (11%), vertigo - 2 (5%), reduction of phons mood (children under 7 years old emotional labiality, whimpering) - 5 (13%), social disorientation (lack of regular friends, loss of contact with teachers and peers) - 3 (8%), increased sweating - 5 (13%), night extirpation - 3 (8%).

Results and discussion. YRA performed ENMG on 10 patients (25%). Changes in ENMG in patients with YRA were reported in most cases (60%) a decrease in the number of ENMG tests by n.medianus, n.radialis 30% and n. ulnaris (10%), not the M-response amplitude called stimulation of a more distal area, decreased (partial block of conduct). In YRA, EEG was performed on 30 patients (75%). Changes in YRA treatment were diffuse in most cases (90%). Out of 10 patients with epileptic seizures spontaneous epileptic activity was detected on EEG in only 12.5% of cases (5 patients), one patient showed focal changes against the background of diffuse bioelectrical changes in brain activity, The rest of the patients had only diffuse changes in the intercourse period.

Conclusions. Neural system damage occurs in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis 48.9% The most frequent clinical variants are cephalgicity (37.5%), sensory sphere disturbance (17.5%) and cramping (15%) and systemic redness of cognitive disorders (51%), cephalgicity (40%), convulsions (33%) social dislocation (20%), violation of sensitive spheres (6.7%).

Literature:

1. Gowdie, P.J., Tse, S.M.L. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis / P.J. Gowdie, S.M.L. Tse // *Pediatr. Clin. North Am.* – 2012. – Vol. 59. – № 2. – P. 301–327.
2. Heiligenhaus A. Review for disease of the year: epidemiology of juvenile idiopathic arthritis and its associated uveitis: the probable risk factors / A. Heiligenhaus [et al.] // *Ocul. Immunol. Inflamm.* – 2013. – Vol. 21. – № 3. – P. 180–191.
3. Hermann, G. Comorbidity of type 1 diabetes and juvenile idiopathic arthritis / G. Hermann // *J. Pediatr.* – 2015. – Vol. 166. – № 4. – P. 930–935.